

MICROSTRUCTURE-SENSITIVE ENVIRO-MECHANICAL RESPONSE CHARACTERIZATION AND SIMULATION IN SiC/SiC CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

SiC/SiC continuous fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) can exhibit a wide range of microstructure variability that arises from multiple unique processing routes (e.g., chemical vapour infiltration (CVI), polymer infiltration pyrolysis (PIP), melt infiltration (MI)). Service conditions of the targeted applications for these SiC/SiC CMCs produce a complex enviro-mechanical response. As life limiting damage initiation is often related to the weakest link or coupled extreme value microstructure attributes (e.g., pores, fibre clusters, secondary matrix phases) that conspire to produce the greatest driving force for damage initiation and propagation, this work is seeking to understand the relationship between local microstructure, microstructure variability, and the extreme value or anomalous attributes of the microstructure that have the most significant influence on the overall response. Here a set of automated tools have been developed to characterize the key microstructure attributes hypothesized to have the greatest influence on the damage response. Advanced segmentation and feature extraction algorithms are employed to separate out the various constituent phases, identify key attributes or features of interest and digitize the microstructure of the CMCs. Specific metrics are then defined to quantify the structural attributes and features of interest. Algorithms have also been developed to identify anomalous and/or extreme value attributes that are hypothesised to promote damage. Statistical volume elements (SVE) that sample the distributions of the microstructure attributes of interest are generated and discrete damage models along with environmental damage models are being developed to capture the microstructure-sensitive enviro-mechanical response. Experimental verification/validation is performed via specialized experimental techniques that identify

areas in the material where damage initiates through acoustic emission detection (AE) and digital image correlation (DIC). Targeted 3D materials characterization of these damaged microstructure regions inform the stochastic models employed to describe the extreme value and/or anomalous microstructure attributes of interest.

1 INTRODUCTION

SiC continuous fibre reinforced SiC ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) offer higher temperature capability and lower density than Ni-base superalloys for hot section engine components such as combustor liners, shrouds, stationary vanes and potentially even as rotating turbine blades in the hot section of gas turbine engines. Several gas turbine engine manufactures are considering this technology for their next generation of commercial engines [1, 2]. Despite the interest in SiC/SiC CMCs there is still much to be understood regarding the physics of the fundamental damage processes that occur over time in operational environments. Here a variety of tools and approaches are being developed to characterize the fundamental structure of SiC/SiC CMCs, understand of how that structure is linked to the operant damage mechanisms, and develop physics based models to capture the enviro-mechanical response. Additionally, experimental techniques are being developed to monitor damage in situ and understand how the local microstructure is related to the operant damage modes.

2 MICROSTRUCTURE CHARACTERIZATION AND ANOMALY DETECTION SPECIFICATIONS

2.1 Data collection and data processing

Characterizing the microstructure and understanding how defects, secondary phases or microstructural anomalies influence material toughness is an important step in linking CMC processing techniques to overall component strength. Depending on the processing route, a hierarchy of microstructural features are produced that can have varying degrees of influence of the overall response. Here the focus is on how the structure of the continuous fibre reinforcement may influence the damage response. Fibres can be considered at two length scales: individual fibres within the tows, and collections of fibres among the tows. Characterization of the stochastic nature of the textile weave and the individual filaments has been performed via μ CT previously. For example, Bale et al. derived a set of expressions to describe statistical deviations from a nominally periodic weave structure [3]. Fast et al. employed a variety of topological and Euclidean metrics to characterize the statistical aspects of fibre placement within a single tow [4]. These works demonstrate that although the structure can be quite complex, reasonable metrics can be employed to quantify the structure. Once available, these same metrics can be employed to link the stochastic structure with the response.

Here various techniques are demonstrated to quantify the structure of the SiC/SiC composite S200 after it has been exposed thermally (see Figure 1) [5]. First, the individual fibres are quantified using pertinent scalar, vector, and tensor fields. Then an algorithm for identifying regions in the quantified microstructure attribute fields that are inconsistent with the nominal field behaviour is demonstrated. In this manner, the inconsistent or anomalous regions can be identified. Simulation can then be employed to understand the anomalies relative to their influence on the response. Specifically, in this work a continuously varying fibre orientation field is constructed based on the orientation of the individual fibres. Understanding the statistics of the individual fibres and their orientation provides insight into the variability of the structure of the fibre tows. Knowledge of fibre orientation can also give insight into local defects such as pores. In other words, anomalous behaviour of the individual fibre orientation may be associated with the emergence of other defects in the region. Quantification of a fibre orientation field in real micrographs of composites requires extensive image processing including the segmentation, feature extraction, and tracking the fibres in 3D when 3D data is available.

Images analysed in this work were collected from the material S200 which is composed of Nicalon™ fibres in amorphous SiNC matrix. The layup of the composite consisted of layers of 8 harness satin weave fabric with a $[0/90/0/90]_{\text{sym}}$ stacking sequence processed by polymer impregnation and pyrolysis at COI Ceramics Inc., San Diego, CA [6]. Data was collected in three dimensions via a RoboMet.3D automated serial sectioning system manufactured by UES Inc. 4401 Dayton-Xenia Rd.

Dayton, OH 45432. The sample was captured in a series of images with a 10% overlap such that the images could be combined into a single high magnification montage. Each layer of the material is approximately 1 μ m in depth, and sectioned at 45° between the 0° and 90° fibre directions such that the fibre cross sections are all elliptical for both 0° and 90° oriented fibres. Details of image alignment, feature extraction of the fibre objects, and fibre tracking in 3D is given elsewhere [5]. In this manner, the positions and orientation of the fibres are quantified in 3D as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Stitched montage of 36 optical images of the SiC/SiC CMC S200 taken at 320x magnification after a thermal exposure in an oxidizing environment. The average fiber diameter is 20 μ m.

Figure 2. 3D Fibre track containing 3 tows

2.2 Constructing data fields

To construct vector fields for anomaly detection, the concept of a velocity fields was employed from fluid dynamics. Specifically, each fibre is modelled as a fluid streamer within the piecewise continuous velocity field at steady state. In other words, the velocity vector field is modelled as a smoothly varying continuum, where fibre positions behave as discrete samples of the vector field. Differentiation is performed with respect to depth into the serial sectioned specimen (instead of with respect to time) or $dx/dz, dy/dz$ where x and y denote the position in the section plane and z denotes the depth at which the current section is taken relative to the overall specimen. Therefore, in this case velocity refers to the rate at which a fibre's position is changing with respect to the depth of the imagined plane.

In fluid dynamics, the 'features' of a flow, such as eddies, boundary layers, etc. are described as gradients of the velocity vector. A similar approach is employed here where a 'velocity gradients' is constructed to describe the features of the homogenous velocity field. Specifically, the velocity gradient tensor field describes how velocity is changing with respect to position in the sample. It is assumed here that the material can be modelled as a smoothly varying velocity field. The gradient tensor field is then locally approximated as a truncated Taylor's according to:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{x,n(i,j)} - v_{x,i} &\approx \frac{\partial v_{x,i}}{\partial x} (x_{n(i,j)} - x_i) + \frac{\partial v_{x,i}}{\partial y} (y_{n(i,j)} - y_i) \\ v_{y,n(i,j)} - v_{y,i} &\approx \frac{\partial v_{y,i}}{\partial x} (x_{n(i,j)} - x_i) + \frac{\partial v_{y,i}}{\partial y} (y_{n(i,j)} - y_i), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $v_{x,i} = dx_i/dz$ and $v_{x,n(i,j)} = dx_{n(i,j)}/dz$ for the i^{th} fiber and $n(i,j)$ refers to j^{th} neighbor of the i^{th} fiber. Similar notation is employed here for the derivatives of y . There are N total fibers and J_i total neighbors for the i^{th} fiber such that enumeration can be expressed as $i = 1 \dots N$ for the fibers and $j = 1 \dots J_i$ for the neighbors of the i^{th} fiber. Representing differences in position as $\Delta x(i,j) = x_{n(i,j)} - x_i$, and similarly with velocity, the equation can be expressed in matrix form. Inserting the discretely sampled data from the velocity field yields the equation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta x(i, 1) & \Delta y(i, 1) \\ \Delta x(i, 2) & \Delta y(i, 2) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \Delta x(i, J_i) & \Delta y(i, J_i) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial v_{x,i}}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_{y,i}}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_{x,i}}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial v_{y,i}}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta v_x(i, 1) & \Delta v_y(i, 1) \\ \Delta v_x(i, 2) & \Delta v_y(i, 2) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \Delta v_x(i, J_i) & \Delta v_y(i, J_i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i \hat{\mathbf{G}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i,$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial v_{x,i}}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_{y,i}}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_{x,i}}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial v_{y,i}}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

is the estimated gradient describing how the velocity field changes with position.

The gradient $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_i$ is not directly observable and is determined through least squares fitting, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_i = (\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i^T \hat{\mathbf{A}}_i)^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_i^T \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i$. Borrowing from notions of material mechanics, $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_i$ describes the transformation applied to the position to give the change in velocity field and can be split into separate symmetric and anti-symmetric components. The symmetric part of the gradient, $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{sym} = 1/2 (\hat{\mathbf{G}}_i + \hat{\mathbf{G}}_i^T)$, describes an affine transformation with no rotation or displacement while the anti-symmetric part, $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{anti} = 1/2 (\hat{\mathbf{G}}_i - \hat{\mathbf{G}}_i^T)$ describes a rotational affine transformation. Here in this work, the focus is on the symmetric part of the gradient $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{sym}$ that physically describes shear and expansion or contraction between the individual fibres. In this manner, the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{sym}$ describe the magnitude and direction of the principle directions of expansion or compaction. If locally the fibres are all perfectly aligned along their axes, the eigenvalues are zero. In a neighbourhood under uniform expansion, the eigenvalues will be equal and positive. Conversely uniform contraction locally will be quantified by eigenvalues that are equal and negative. In the case of shear, the eigenvalues will be unequal. In this way, the eigenvalues can be interpreted to describe the characteristics of local variations in the microstructure. Applying algorithms for anomaly detection to these fields give insight into local structure that is unique relative to the nominal structure.

2.3 Anomaly Detection Algorithm

It is hypothesised here that certain microstructural anomalies can play a significant role in the operant damage processes that drive material degradation and failure. Understanding and controlling such anomalies may help to improve overall material performance. To determine anomalies in a field, a feature vector is first considered, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{V}_i = [V_{k1}, V_{k2}, \dots, V_K]^T, \quad (4)$$

such that it is composed of K features for each fiber i . For detecting anomalies within the velocity field, the feature vector is composed of $v_{x,i}$ and $v_{y,i}$. For detecting anomalies within the velocity gradient, the feature vector \mathbf{V}_i is constructed based on the angle of principle eigenvector and trace of $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{sym}$. The nominal behaviour can be modelled several ways including: supervised, semi-supervised, and unsupervised. In supervised approaches, training data is employed to formulate the background model, where either no anomaly contamination is present or the classification is already known. This approach is not effective when there is a limited notion of what or where an anomaly might be, which happens to be the case here. Without manual classification of a background model, an unsupervised approach must be employed. Unsupervised approaches to background modelling allow contamination of the set as long as the background to anomaly ratio is sufficiently large. As the ratio increases the background model is less influenced by anomalies, and the model is more likely to accurately capture the nominal background. Acceptable ratios tend to be somewhere on the order of 100:1. The primary focus of this work is on the individual fibres. The particular dataset considered here contains approximately 21,000 fibres, which constitutes a very large number of background points.

The probability density function employed here to model the background or nominal set is based on a multivariate Gaussian mixture model with K dimensions. A mixture model such as the one employed here allows the background to contain multiple clusters which is critical due to the bi-modal nature of the fibre weave. The Gaussian mixture model is defined as

$$p(\mathbf{v}_i) = \sum_{m=1}^M w_m f_m(\mathbf{v}_i | \boldsymbol{\mu}_m, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_m) \quad (5)$$

where each mixture component f_m is a Gaussian weighted, w_m , such that the sum of all weights equals unity. While the optimal number of components, m , can be estimated [7], the computational cost can be very high and the number of components can be overestimated without negative effects. Each Gaussian component is given by

$$f_m(\mathbf{v}_i | \boldsymbol{\mu}_m, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_m) = (2\pi)^{-k/2} |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_m|^{-1/2} \times \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{v}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_m)^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_m^{-1} (\mathbf{v}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_m)\right] \quad (6)$$

where mean and covariance of the m^{th} component are given by $\boldsymbol{\mu}_m$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_m$, respectively [7]. The covariance matrix is of size $K \times K$ where K is the number of dimensions in the model. A multivariate model is advantageous to single dimension models because more information is present for calculating a model and separating clusters. Here, the mixture model is computed using the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm [8]. A decision threshold is chosen in the tails of the distribution such that the probability of occurrence is less than 0.01 percent. Any sample points with a P-value smaller than the threshold are classified as anomalies, and therefore not belonging to the model.

2.4 Results

To visualize the results a HSV colour-model is employed where each fibre is assigned a colour based on the orientation and magnitude of the velocity vector. Hue in the HSV model is circular allowing angle of fibre velocity to directly correspond to an angle of hue as shown in Figure 3(b). Saturation, which describes how vibrant a colour appears, represents the magnitude of the velocity. In Figure 3(a), a segmented sub-section of a layer is given where fibres are coloured according to velocity as just described. From the figure, the different 0° and 90° oriented fibres are easily visualized. Additionally, it is interesting to note that there is some variability even within the tows where all the fibres are nominally oriented similarly as can be seen by the slight variations in the colours within the tows.

Figure 3. a) Segmentation colored according to velocity, b) Direction/Hue legend, c) Voronoi tessellation colored according to velocity gradient. Shear bands are present between tows.

The velocity gradient is visualized in a similar manner. Though the gradient is computed for a given radius around a fibre, visualization is set up by assigning a unique neighbourhood for each fibre based on a Voronoi diagram. In this manner, the cells centred around each fibre is coloured according to the symmetric component of the gradient, $\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{sym}$. The hue is determined by the direction of the principle eigenvector and saturation indicates the difference in the eigenvalues computed for each Voronoi cell. Value in the HSV colour scheme is determined by the trace of the symmetric gradient, or sum of computed eigenvalues and visualized by the darkness of each cell. Figure 3(c) depicts the velocity gradient with shear bands coloured according to the direction of shear. Dark or light regions exist where fibres are contracting or expanding locally resulting in negative or positive eigenvalues

respectively. Speckling, or significant differences in the colour scheme from one Voronoi cell to the next is a result of high noise in the data that results from the discrete sampling of the gradient field. Noise is reduced by increasing the neighbourhood size used in computation of the gradient, but neighbourhoods that are too large can obscure small anomalies. In this work, a neighbourhood sized three times the average nearest neighbour distance was found to sufficiently smooth the gradient. Neighbourhoods that are converging or diverging are easily distinguishable within the gradient, while local neighbourhood noise is low.

Figure 4. a) Gaussian mixture estimated PDF of the velocity field, b) Ellipses classified as anomalies,

Anomaly detection is applied to both the velocity field and its gradient. In Figure 4(a) the bivariate Gaussian mixture model estimated to fit the velocity field data from the S200 dataset is shown. Points that lie in the tails are labelled as anomalies and mapped back to the fibres in the image. Detected anomalies within the velocity field typically correspond to fibres that have a higher aspect ratio and thus a higher orientation angle. The numbered fibres in Figure 4(b) correspond to the numbered anomalies in the PDF. The fibres with high orientation angle are often found along tow boundaries that have greater freedom to shift during the weaving process. Although fibres with anomalous velocity are identified, it is likely that the effect of individual fibres on material properties is much less significant than that of groups of fibres which can be determined by examination of the velocity gradient.

Figure 5. a) Gaussian mixture estimated PDF of the velocity field, b) Ellipses classified as anomalies

Anomaly detection of the velocity gradient is accomplished by modelling the PDF of the direction of principle eigenvector and trace (sum of eigenvalues) of \mathbf{G}_{sym} . Incorporation of the direction of principle eigenvector allows detection of areas where fibers are expanding or contracting in anomalous directions. On the other hand, incorporation of the sum of eigenvalues mutes pure shear while

emphasizing expansion or contraction. The Gaussian estimated PDF for the velocity gradient and the corresponding numbered anomalies can be seen in Figures 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. Each Voronoi cell is centred on a fibre and is coloured according to the gradient of the surrounding neighbourhood. The observed 'X' shape of the distribution is a result of higher expansion along regions undergoing imperfect shear near the tow boundaries. Points far from the origin and not located within one of the arms of the 'X' correspond to expansion in that direction. Anomalies identified from both anomaly tests typically coincide with tow edges. However, the anomalies detected in the velocity gradient give insight into general aspects of the overall structure.

At the leading/trailing edge of a tow, the fibres in neighbouring tows either diverge or converge to accommodate the new tow. Anomaly detection of the velocity gradient consistently labels these regions as anomalous, as seen circled in red in Figure 5(b). Many of the smaller regions, such as the region indicated by the orange oval, are not consistent through the sample thickness and likely correlate to noise inherent in discrete sampling. Other anomalous regions have been found to correlate to the appearance of a pore. As the pore grows, when moving through the thickness of the sample, nearby fibres are displaced and found during anomaly detection as converging regions. Areas of high convergence are of special interest due to the strength differential between matrix and fibre coatings. As fibres contract, it is more likely that they will touch each other via the coatings that surround each fibre. Due to the fact that the fibre coating is so much weaker than the fibre or the matrix, it is hypothesized that large interconnections of fibre coatings can provide an easy crack propagation path through a fibre tow. The area circled in blue in Figure 5(b) is of interest because it was not detected by inspection prior to applying the anomaly detection algorithm. This area may signify the emergence of a pore in the nearby light region where fibres are diverging, though the sample is not deep enough to determine the cause.

3 ENVIRO-MECHANICAL MICROSTRUCTURE-SENSITIVE DAMAGE MODELING

3.1 Discrete damage modeling of statistical volume elements

Figure 6. Setup for a 2D simulation for a statistical volume element embedded into a boundary region of material with effective properties.

It is well understood that microstructure variability has a direct impact on the variability of response. Previous work has been performed employing FEM simulation of multiple statistical volume elements (SVE) to characterize the influence varying microstructure can have on variability of damage response like fatigue [9-11]. Each statistical volume element for a desired response (i.e., fracture at the

fibre scale) is designed to be large enough such that the response parameter of interest at a particular location is unaffected by statistical variations in the microstructure at distances on the order of the size of the volume (i.e., correlation length is less than size of SVE); however, the volume is not so large that it contains a statistically representative set of responses for that particular response parameter. The concept of an SVE contrast to that of a representative volume element (RVE) and is defined such that the distribution of local response or effective response of the volume will not change based on where the RVE is sampled from the microstructure ensemble (i.e., bulk material), or if it is further increased in size. In some cases, information obtained from multiple SVEs can constitute a RVE level characterization.

In the work discussed here, multiple SVEs consisting of arrays of distributed unidirectional continuous fibres were generated and embedded into a homogeneous volume to explore how variation in the local fibre spacing affects transverse crack growth. The basic setup of the 2D simulations with applied plane strain boundary conditions is shown in Figure 6. For these particular SVEs, the position of the fibres was random and the fibre radius was assumed to follow a known distribution.

Simulations were carried out by means of the XFEM capabilities of the standard finite element package Abaqus®, [12]. The instantiated statistical volume element is embedded into a homogenized material in order to avoid boundary effects that appear if loading is applied to the statistical volume element itself. The applied initial crack is also inserted only into the homogenized material, not the SVE. In this manner, the simulations initiate with a stress concentration at the boundary of the SVE without altering the SVE itself. Fibre coatings were modelled as thin layers around the individual fibres, one-element thick. The material properties employed used in these simulations are shown in Table 1 below and were taken from [13]. These properties are representative of the SiC/SiC CMC HiPerComp® produced by GE Aviation, Evendale, OH processed via a melt infiltration (MI) process. The boundary region was assigned properties representative of the matrix properties as described in Table 1, but with a much higher initiation stress to avoid initiation of additional cracks in the region.

Table 1. Properties of HiPerComp® SiC-SiC CMCs

Matrix
Elastic properties $E=360$ GPa, $\nu=0.185$
Initiation stress $\sigma_I=0.8$ GPa (maximum principal)
Fracture energy 36 J/m ²
Tolerance 0.05; Damage stabilization 0.005
Interphase (BN)
Elastic properties $E=10$ GPa, $\nu=0.05$
Initiation stress $\sigma_I=75$ MPa (maximum principal)
Fracture energy 5 J/m ²
Tolerance 0.05; Damage stabilization 0.01
Fiber
Elastic properties $E=380$ GPa, $\nu=0.185$
Initiation stress $\sigma_I=2.6$ GPa (maximum principal)
Fracture energy 50 J/m ²
Tolerance 0.05; Damage stabilization 0.005

Typical simulation results are shown in Figure 7. These simulations provide some valuable insight into the mechanisms of crack propagation in unidirectional composites. For example, it was observed in all cases that advancing cracks initiate secondary cracks in fibre coatings at a finite distance from its tip as shown in Figure 8(a). However, these simulations also brought to light a severe limitation with the current XFEM capability in ABAQUS®. Specifically, the current implementation of the XFEM in ABAQUS® does not allow for crack coalescence. Physically, the secondary cracks that initiate in the fibre coating will eventually intersect and coalesce with the primary crack, but numerically this is not allowed in the software. Consider, for instance, the simulation shown in Figure 8(b). The secondary crack grows up to the primary crack, but the program cannot merge them. As a result, the few elements that remain separating the primary crack from the secondary crack are artificially stiff and alter the energy and stress state of the entire simulation. In the end, these artefacts precluded fracture

energy comparisons between different instantiations necessary to determine which microstructural features are critical for the overall strength of the microstructure. New discrete damage modelling approaches are currently being developed that avoid this limitation (cf. [14]). However, due to the current limitations the full impact of the variability of fibre diameter and placement on the transverse fracture response was undetermined.

Figure 7. Example simulations for two different instantiations of SVE

As a result of these simulations and realization of the inadequacy of current crack modelling approaches, our group is working on the development of crack growth and crack intersection simulation mechanisms into mechanical simulation package BSAM. This software will be used for future simulations. Additionally, the initiation of secondary cracks in the coatings at a finite distance from the primary crack tip prevalent in our simulations (Figure 8) resulted in an investigation into crack deflection mechanism in ceramic-matrix composites [15].

Figure 8. (a) Secondary crack initiation inside fibre coating at a distance from the tip of advancing crack and (b) Two cracks growing to intersection and apparent coalescence.

3.2 Environmental damage modeling of SiC/SiC composites

SiC/SiC composites are actively considered for use in high temperature gas turbine engines with use temperatures in the 1200-1400°C range. However, they may be vulnerable to environmentally-assisted degradation and failure at intermediate temperatures (700-1000°C) due to a combination of thermomechanical and chemical mechanisms including the ingress of oxidant through matrix cracks, oxidation and volatilization of fibre coatings, and the potentially volatilization-enhanced oxidation of the subsequently exposed fibre [16-18]. At higher temperatures, a change in the mechanism of oxidation from passive to active due to the enhanced role of volatile oxide products can occur with potentially debilitating consequences [19]. Oxidation of SiC involves a volume change by a factor of 2.2, which produces large growth stresses that can influence thermomechanical failure mechanisms. This necessitates a fundamental understanding of SiC oxide growth and the stresses generated therein

at the aforementioned temperatures. Here, a combined modelling and experimental approach is introduced to address these issues. Preliminary results are then given based on applying the introduced model for the oxidation of a SiC plate, and from measurements of oxidation growth stresses using the experimental approach.

Thermal oxidation of SiC is a coupled thermomechanics and transport problem, and involves several key phenomena, including absorption and diffusion of oxidant and effluent gases through the SiO₂ scale. Diffusion of both the oxidant and effluent gasses are affected by the stress in the scale, the generation of residual stresses owing to the volume change upon oxidation and the viscoelastic/plastic flow that accommodates much of this volume change. They are also affected by the magnitude and time-evolution of the oxide stresses and oxidation reaction at the SiC/SiO₂ interface that is also affected by the stress at this interface. All these phenomena are included in the model developed here through well-established physics-based prescriptions for each of them. These include: (i) A Henrian law for solubility of oxidant/effluent gas species in the silica scale [20], (ii) Oxidant diffusivities and oxidation reaction rates that conform to Deal-Grove kinetics [21, 22] with modifications for their dependence on stresses [23], (iii) A Maxwell solid description of the viscoelastic glass scale with a viscosity dependent on stress according to Eyring's description [23, 24]. The details of the model will be published at a future date.

In Figure 9, the equibiaxial stress generated in the SiO₂ scale is plotted relative to position through the thickness for the thermal oxidation of a thick SiC plate at 800°C. These results were obtained from simulations where the full volume change upon oxidation was employed to describe the mismatch strain. The physical mechanisms describing instantaneous accommodation of a part of this volume change were not included. Figure 9(a) shows that extremely large compressive stresses exist right at the SiC/SiO₂ interface ($z = 0$), owing to the large volume expansion accompanying oxidation. These stresses more quickly relax when the glass is less viscous and subject to large stresses, which follows the Eyring prescription. Figure 9(b) shows that the average equibiaxial stress relaxes with time owing to viscoelastic flow; however, stresses as large as 2 GPa can persist even after thousand hours of oxidation. Oxidation at higher temperatures produces qualitatively similar stress distributions and are not shown here. However, the magnitudes of growth stresses generated by higher temperature oxidation are considerably smaller (e.g. nearly all of the growth stress is relaxed by viscoelastic relaxation, upon oxidation for even an hour at 1200°C). These results are consistent with recently published results for oxidation of SiC [25, 26].

Figure 9 (a) Variation in biaxial stress along the thickness of the thermally grown SiO₂ scale for varying oxide thicknesses / oxidation periods, and, (b) Average biaxial stress in the scale as a function of oxidation time, for SiC oxidation at 800C.

The experimental approach adopted here employs the following sequence of steps: (i) A capture of the deviation from flatness of unoxidized SiC plates via laser interferometry, (ii) Isothermal oxidation

of SiC plates at prescribed oxidation temperatures and time-periods in dry oxygen, followed by a cool-down in an inert atmosphere to room temperature, (iii) Selective etching of oxide on one side of the plate, (iv) Measurement of the displacement field of the oxidized and etched plate, and, (v) Extraction of the misfit strain or residual stress by comparing the deformation field of the substrate to those obtained from mechanics models for the deformation of a plate by misfit residual stresses generated in a thin film atop it. The first step allows a proper account of the warping of thin SiC plates due to polishing and other processes used to make them. Laser interferometry is employed to measure the displacements of the SiC plate. Since the substrate displacements are measured following a cool-down to room temperature, stresses due to thermal expansion mismatch are subtracted to get a proper account of oxidation growth stresses. It has been verified that at the intermediate temperatures of interest here, 700-1000°C, the relaxation of the thermal (and oxidation) stress that occurs during cool-down is smaller than the error bars associated with the measurement of the stresses. An exercise of the experimental procedure demonstrated that growth stresses of magnitude 200 ± 20 MPa persist following growth of an oxide 100 nm thick at 800°C, while negligibly small stresses are found after the growth of a similarly thick oxide at 1200°C.

The measured stresses at 800°C are significantly smaller than those found from the simulations (see Figure 9). These can be attributed to the fact that the entire volume expansion upon oxidation is used to prescribe the misfit strain associated with oxidation. It is hypothesized that a large part of this volume expansion is instantaneously accommodated through plastic flow of the glass, a process whose atomistic mechanisms are not fully understood. Indeed, an exercise of the developed model (not shown here) with an empirical mismatch strain that is 1% of that due to the volume expansion predicts stresses similar to those measured in our experiments at 800°C. Another factor that may contribute to this disparity is the uncertainty in the viscosity data, especially considering that viscosity is significantly affected by small amounts of impurities, including possibly C-based interstitials in the glass scale that are emitted by the SiC substrate during oxidation. Parametric studies are currently underway wherein the viscosity and the oxidation mismatch strain are varied over ranges consistent with the uncertainty in their knowledge, to understand their effects on the predicted oxidation stresses. Additionally, detailed models are also being exercised that include physics-based prescriptions for this instantaneous accommodation of the volume expansion upon oxidation to understand the physical mechanisms underlying this observation. Future extensions of this work will consider oxidation at curved geometries characteristic of fibre-reinforced composites, oxidation at crack fronts, and in atmospheres where volatile species are present.

4 IN SITU DAMAGE MONITORING

In CMCs, the matrix is typically somewhat weaker than the fibers and is the first constituent to fail when exposed to sufficient loads. As discussed previously, cracking of the matrix can lead to exposure of the load bearing fibers to harsh environments and more rapid structural failure. The rate at which the environment infiltrates the material may very well be a function of how matrix cracking has occurred. Here various experimental techniques are being employed to determine the relationship between in-situ crack signals or acoustic emissions measured in a MI SiC/SiC CMC during monotonic and dwell loading to the amount of matrix cracks over a certain area (matrix crack density) in the material.

The development of large matrix cracks is also known to affect the material stiffness and when local microstructure influences crack growth, it results in a non-uniform strain distribution. Non-uniform strain fields on the surface can directly be measured via digital image correlation (DIC). DIC gives insight on how matrix cracking has affected localized portions of the material and can provide a guide for quantifying the acoustic emission (AE) signals. Areas of high localized strain precede the failure location when specimens are loaded to failure. An example of the type of results obtained using this method is given in Figure 10. After failure, the energy density of the AE signals was considered relative to the failure location to determine if any significant patterns could be determined. Additionally, the DIC results were compared to the AE results to determine any correlation that could be determined between the two techniques that might give early indications regarding the location of ultimate failure. Although apparent indications with both the AE and DIC correlated with the ultimate

failure location, these indications were not necessarily unique. It is hypothesized that detailed microstructural characterization may better inform these techniques and give better insight as to why the material eventually failed at one location instead of another.

Figure 10. (a) Energy density of AE events plotted for Time (sec) versus location (mm) along the gage section, (b) the DIC results highlighting local strain concentrations, and (c) the energy density of the AE events plotted for stress (MPa) versus location (mm) along the gage section

To this end, techniques are being developed to link local damage to the local microstructure. Samples that have been loaded beyond the matrix cracking stress are being optically imaged under load so that the matrix cracks are open and are more easily observed. In Figure 11, a cross section is shown of a MI SiC/SiC composite with the individual cracks traced in red. Using these techniques, the cracks are considered relative to the local microstructure to determine what microstructure attributes are predominate at the failure locations. To assist these studies, other techniques are also being employed that use UV fluorescent dye penetrant to highlight the crack paths for easier segmentation as can be seen in Figure 12. Once the cracks infiltrated with UV dye penetrant are imaged and segmented, the crack paths can be overlaid on the optical micrographs taken under nominal light conditions to study the influence of the local microstructure on local crack initiation and growth. Other useful information such as crack density measurements can be readily obtained from these techniques which can be used to verify other approaches for crack density measurements.

Figure 11: Matrix crack highlighted in RED for a MI SiC/SiC system loaded in tension

Figure 12: Matrix cracks imaged using a dye penetrant under ultraviolet light

Estimation of the matrix crack density using cumulative AE energy has been performed and showed correlation to manual determination of the density [27]. Here, the AE data is used to highlight the initiation and distribution of the matrix crack density and, with the help of DIC, can estimate the

localized effect of crack growth. Results have shown that areas where AE signal clusters correspond well with areas of high localized strain [28]. For instance, once the matrix cracking stress range is exceeded during tensile loading, cracking is distributed evenly if the microstructure along the gage length has no distinct variation. However, a drastic change in microstructure can cause a weak spot in the material where significantly more cracking occurs compared to a nominal microstructure region, as seen in Figure 10. Localized energy regions beyond the proportional limit and near failure are attributed to fiber failure related phenomenon.

Once the link between AE and material response is established and validated using DIC, an investigation can be done into the initiation of major matrix cracks at lower stresses, which may be too low to detect any strain deviation via DIC. Lower stresses are typically employed for fatigue and high temperature testing. Also, a detailed study is planned using finite element analysis (FEA) to quantify the variation in signal characteristics as a function of depth [29].

5 CONCLUSIONS

Here various methods are described to understand how local microstructural variability influences fracture initiation and propagation in CMCs. First, a detailed approach is described to quantify various field quantities in continuous fibre reinforced composites to quantify local microstructure variations. Specifically, velocity field and velocity gradients are developed to describe the relative orientations of the fibres. Visualization of the velocity field immediately distinguishes separate tows and fibre directions, as well as highlighting slight variations in orientation within tows. Visualization of the gradient utilizes all three colour-channels of the HSV model. Anomaly detection results of both fields pinpoint areas that are inconsistent with the background model and require further investigation. It is hypothesized that analysis of anomalies for multiple layup processes and weave types will lead to better understanding of how processing techniques affect the microstructure. Next a methodology to simulate the influence of microstructure variation on local fracture processes using SVE was demonstrated with the XFEM approach. Additionally, physics based models are being developed to capture environmental degradation of SiC/SiC CMCs at intended operating temperatures. Finally, several techniques are being explored for in situ damage monitoring for model validation and to better understand the microstructure attributes that have the most influence on the dominate damage processes.

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